

Kinetic Study of Copper (II) lysine Complex by Hexa Cyano Ferrate (III) Ion in Alkaline Medium

Paper Id : 20756 Submission Date : 2025-10-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-10-14 Publication Date : 2025-10-18

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17430968

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Abstract

The kinetics of the oxidation of an amino acid-metal complex called copper (II) lysine (CLC) by the alkali hexacyanoferrate (III) was studied over a temperature range of 303K-323K. The rate depended on the first power of the substrate concentration and was zero-order with respect to the oxidant hexacyanoferrate (III) (HCF). The reaction rate increased with increasing alkali concentration over various ranges. The reaction proceeds in the fast phase via the formation of a substrate and oxidant complex, which then rapidly converts to the corresponding keto acid—6-amino-2-oxohexanoic acid, copper (II) oxide, and ammonia. The reaction rate increased with increasing ionic strength.

Keywords

Kinetics, Oxidation, Copper (II) lysine, Hexacyanoferrate (III)

Introduction

The study of the amino acids and their metal complexes that make up humans and animals is one of the most exciting areas of chemistry. Therefore, amino acids and their metal complexes have been studied with various oxidants. Oxidation reactions play a major role in organic synthesis^{7,14,16}.

Lysine is an essential amino acid that plays a vital role in promoting human growth, enhancing immune function, and improving central nervous system function^{8,20}. Furthermore, along with calcium and other nutrients, lysine plays a positive role in the formation of collagen^{2,20}.

Objective of study

The objective of the present work is to study the formation of the copper (II) lysine complex and its oxidation by the hexacyanoferrate (III) ion. The oxidation reaction of the copper (II) lysine complex will be studied in the laboratory using conventional and non-conventional methods for kinetic studies. If possible, the intermediates formed during the reaction will be identified qualitatively and quantitatively and product analysis of almost all substrates will be attempted.

Review of Literature

Copper (II) catalysis for oxidation of L-tryptophan by hexacyanoferrate (III) in alkaline medium: A kinetic and mechanistic approach was studied by Asghar, et al (2017), Disturbances of amino acid metabolism: clinical chemistry and diagnosis was studied by Bremer, et al (1981), Kinetics and mechanism of osmium (VIII) catalyzed oxidation of valine by hexacyanoferrate in alkaline medium was studied by Devra and Yadav (2012), Role of dietary histidine in the prevention of obesity and metabolic syndrome was studied by DiNicolantonio, et al (2018), Simultaneous determination of cephalixin and lysine in their salt using high-performance liquid chromatography of derivatives was studied by Fabregas and Beneyto (1980), Palladium (II)-catalyzed oxidation of L tryptophan by hexacyanoferrate (III) in perchloric acid medium: a kinetic and mechanistic approach was studied by Fawzy (2015), Effect of silver (I) catalyst on the oxidation of L-asparagine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III): a kinetic and mechanistic approach, was studied by Fawzy, et al (2016), Synthesis, characterization of some complexes of copper (II) with L-asparagine, L-histidine, L-lysine was studied by Tripathi and Kamal (2015), etc.

^{16,17}.

Methodology

Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, CuCl₂, and sodium acetate were obtained from Alfa Aesar, Great Britain and used for further purification. Potassium chloride, potassium hydroxide, potassium hydrogen phthalate, oxalic acid, L-lysine, and phenolphthalein were purchased from E. Merck (India) Ltd. and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) was purchased from Fluka-Puris. The purity of lysine, as determined by alkaline titration, was always greater than 99%. All solutions were prepared using triple-distilled water in Pyrex (borosilicate) glass vessels.

Synthesis of Copper (II) lysine complex [CLC]:

Normally, two amino acids combine to form a complex. Therefore, a lysine-copper complex was prepared by reacting the corresponding amino acid (L-lysine) and metal ion in a 1:2 molar ratio in conductivity water. Using from any one of these various copper salts

(Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, CuCl₂) and l-lysine as a ligand, the [Cu(lysine)₂]⁺² complex was prepared. The process involved mixing 2 mM of amino acid with 2 mM of sodium acetate in 20 mL of aqueous solution and stirring until a clear solution was formed. Then, 2 mL of aqueous solution containing 1 mM of metal salt was added dropwise with a wire whisk for 3 hours until a dark blue solution was obtained. Crystallization was carried out in a Petri dish. After a few days, dark blue crystals of [Cu(Lysine)₂]⁺² were observed²¹.

Kinetic Measurements

λ_{max} of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III):

A λ_{max} of 420 nm was recorded for unreacted (0.001 M) potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) with the aid of a double beam Biosync Technology spectrophotometer (model number BST 2800) and an electric-digital spectrophotometer (model number CL-27).

Molar absorption coefficient of potassium hexacyanoferrate (III), rate constant and stoichiometry of the reaction:

At λ_{max} of unreacted potassium hexacyanoferrate, the molar absorption coefficient was found to be 1000 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, which is almost equal to the reported value of 1030 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹^{13,18}. To study the reaction, the absorption capacity of the reaction mixture was measured at increasing times. The rate constant k₀ for each experiment was determined using the formula (Slope/1000): The stoichiometry ratio was 4 : 1 between [hexacyanoferrate (III)] and [substrate]. Hence, the stoichiometric equation for the oxidation of (CLC) is defined as:

Product Analysis:

Copper(II) oxide, 6-amino-2-oxohexanoic acid, and ammonia were found as oxidation products. 6-amino-2-oxohexanoic acid, also known as 6-amino-α-oxo-caproic acid, was confirmed by spot test analysis and infrared spectroscopy. The melting point of 6-amino-2-oxohexanoic acid was found to be 211 °C, while the literature value for this compound is 212 °C. Surface and interface analysis confirmed copper oxide¹⁹. Ammonia was confirmed with the help of Nessler reagent¹².

Result and Discussion

Order with Respect to Hexacyanoferrate (III):

The order of the reaction measured with respect to hexacyanoferrate (III) at constant all other reagentssuch as [CLC], [OH⁻], and [ionic strength] at 30 °C. The hexacyanoferrate was varied two times from 8.0x10⁻⁴ to 16x10⁻⁴ moldm⁻³. Beer's law is not applicable at high concentrations, so a low concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III) was taken.

The absorbance versus time graph was non-linear (Fig. 1) and log (Absorbance) versus time was linear (Fig. 2), respectively, indicating that the first-order of the reaction with respect to oxidant hexacyanoferrate (III). As the [hexacyanoferrate (III)] increases, the value of k₀ remains unchanged, giving further support to the first order with respect to hexacyanoferrate (III).

Fig. 1: Absorbance vs Time plot for the oxidation of CLC

Fig. 2: log (Absorbance) vs Time plot for the oxidation of CLC

Effect of [OH⁻] and Ionic strength on the oxidation of CLC

On increasing the temperature, it was also observed that the reaction deviated from zero order and exhibited complex formation. These reactions were observed at various temperatures ranging from 303 K to 323 K with a difference of 5⁰C. The data and graphs of the above experiments are shown in Table 1 and Figure 3. Standard sodium chloride solutions were used to investigate the effect of ionic strength on the reactions. For CLC, the ionic strength effect showed that as ionic strength increased, the rate constants also increased. The linear graph (Figure 4) between log k and √μ indicated that the reaction occurred between similarity charged ions.

Table 1: Effect of [OH⁻] and ionic strength on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of CLC

10⁴[CLC] = 20.0 mol dm⁻³, 10⁴ [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻ = 10.0 mol dm⁻³ and μ = 2.0 mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	10 ² [OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)				
	1	3	5	7.5	10
	10 ⁻² k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)				
303	9.876	13.224	17.846	19.917	26.945
308	13.876	17.664	19.818	25.142	31.884
313	16.866	20.458	25.018	28.582	37.486
318	21.675	24.678	31.879	33.789	43.908
323	26.102	32.987	36.234	42.765	51.656

Fig. 3: k_o vs [OH⁻] plots for the oxidation of CLC at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318 and 323K

Fig 4: log k_o vs plots for the oxidation of CLC

Dependence of k_o on [CLC]:

The plots k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[CLC]^{-1}$ were gives the straight lines and passes through the origin. These graphs showed that the order was one with respect to CLC (Fig. 5).The values of k_o are shown in Table 2 at five distinct temperatures.

Table 2: Effect of [substrate] on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of CLC.

$10^4[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} = 20.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2[OH^-] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\mu = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Temp. (K)	[SUBSTRATE] (mol dm ⁻³)					
	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.01
	10 ⁻² k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
303	1.382	2.874	3.994	5.855	8.159	11.826
308	2.663	3.196	4.358	8.856	11.984	15.654
313	3.287	4.876	8.345	15.678	19.675	23.834
318	4.543	6.786	9.678	17.876	22.78	26.987
323	6.234	7.987	11.654	21.345	24.765	32.874

Fig. 5: k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[Substrate]^{-1}$ plots for the oxidation of CLC at 303K, 308K, 313K, 318 and 323K

Mechanism of oxidation of Copper (II) lysinecomplex (CLC)¹⁸

the reaction is first order with respect to hexacyanoferrate (III) ion and CLC. the mechanism of the uncatalyzed oxidation of CLC by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) is proposed as:

The rate of the reaction is determined in terms of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III)

Hence,

$$-\frac{d[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 [CLC]^{2-} [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] \quad (5)$$

At high concentration reaction was very fast. So, the lower concentrations of the reactants have been used. Assuming that,

$$[CLC]_T = [CLC] + [CLC]^{2-} \quad (6)$$

Hence,

$$[CLC] = [CLC]_T - [CLC]^{2-} \quad (7)$$

Applying steady state approximation for $[\text{CLC}]^{2-}$

$$\frac{d[\text{CLC}]^{2-}}{dt} = k_1[\text{CLC}][\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CLC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CLC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 0$$

$$\text{or } k_1([\text{CLC}]_T - [\text{CLC}]^{2-})[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CLC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CLC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 0$$

$$k_1[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_1[\text{CLC}]^{2-}[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CLC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CLC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} = 0$$

$$[\text{CLC}]^{2-}(k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}) = k_1[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2$$

$$[\text{CLC}]^{2-} = \frac{k_1[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2}{k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}} \quad (8)$$

As per stoichiometry of the reaction, 4 mol of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ are used per mol of CLC

Hence,

$$k_o = - \frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}} \quad (10)$$

As per experimental conditions and observed results, it can be assumed that

$$k_o = - \frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{k_{-1} + k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and CLC. Now equation (11) can be written as,

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{k_{-1} + k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2}{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{k_1}{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} + \frac{k_{-1}}{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (13)$$

If we plot the value of k_o^{-1} and $[\text{OH}^-]^2$, then the intercept (I) and slope (S) of these plots are given by equations (14) and (15) respectively.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{k_{-1}}{4k_1k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Intercept} = \frac{1}{4k_2[\text{CLC}]_T[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (15)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} = K \quad (16)$$

Where $k_1/k_{-1} = K$ is the equilibrium constant.

Conclusion

Based on the present study, in the uncatalyzed oxidation of the copper(II) glycine complex, the order of reaction is first relative to the hexacyanoferrate(III) ion and the copper(II) glycine complex. The order of reaction relative to $[\text{OH}^-]$ is less than one, as shown by the straight-line plots of k_o versus $[\text{OH}^-]$, which also show that $k_o \propto [\text{OH}^-]$. The graph between $\log k_o$ and $\sqrt{\mu}$ shows that the reaction occurs between ions of like charge, and the rate increases with increasing ionic strength.

Acknowledgement

This study was supported by the Department of Chemistry, S.P.M. College, Udantpuri, Bihar Sharif, a constituent unit of Patliputra University, Patna.

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